

D2.3 INTEGRATED MOLECULAR/MORPHOLOGICAL IDENTIFICATION OF THE SPECIES

Deliverable Number	2.3
Work package Number and Title	WP2 – Ecological, morphological and taxonomic studies for selected species of marine Annelida
Lead Beneficiary	CoNISMa
Version - Status	Final
Due Date	30 April 2024
Deliverable Type	R
Dissemination Level	PU
Internal Reviewer	Kleoniki Keklikoglou, Linda Paternò
Filename	MAPWORMS_D2.3_v14_20240429

DOCUMENT INFO

AUTHORS

Surname	First name	Organization	E-mail
Langeneck	Joachim	CoNISMa	langeneck@conisma.it
Martines	Alessandra	CoNISMa	alessandra.martines@unisalento.it
Putignano	Matteo	CoNISMa	matteo.putignano@unisalento.it
Toso	Andrea	CoNISMa	andrea.toso@unisalento.it
Musco	Luigi	CoNISMa	luigi.musco@unisalento.it

INTERNAL REVIEWERS

Surname	First name	Organization	E-mail
Keklikoglou	Kleoniki	HCMR	keklikoglou@hcmr.gr
Paternò	Linda	SSSA	linda.paterno@santannapisa.it

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Date	Version	Editor	Change	Status
04/03/2024	v1	Joachim Langeneck	Draft of introduction and material and methods	Draft
09/03/2024	v2	Luigi Musco	Revision of introduction and material and methods	Draft
05/04/2024	v3	Joachim Langeneck	Results and conclusions	Draft
16/04/2024	v4	Luigi Musco	Revision	Draft
16/04/2024	v5	Joachim Langeneck	Revision of the whole deliverable	Draft

			- refer- ences	
17/04/2024	v6	Andrea Toso	Revision of the whole deliverable	Draft
17/04/2024	v7	Matteo Putignano	Revision of the whole deliverable	Draft
17/04/2024	v8	Alessandra Martines	Revision of the whole deliverable	Draft
18/04/2024	v9	Joachim Langeneck	Implemen- tation of the suggested changes	Draft
20/04/2024	v10	Kleoniki Kek- likoglou	Internal Re- vision	Draft
22/04/2024	v11	Joachim Langeneck	Correction following internal re- vision	Draft
24/04/2024	v12	Linda Paternò	Internal re- vision	Draft
26/04/2024	v13	Joachim Langeneck	Correction following internal re- vision	Draft
28/04/2024	V14	Arianna Men- ciassi	Review and Approval	Final
29/04/2024	v14	Arianna Men- ciassi	Submission	Final

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1 Introduction	5
1.1 Integrative taxonomy to unravel the diversity of organisms	5
1.2 Integrative taxonomy to unravel the diversity of marine annelids	9
2 Material and methods	10
2.1 Sample Collection and Preservation	10
2.2 Genetic Characterization.....	11
3 Results	12
4 Conclusions	28
5 References	29

1 INTRODUCTION

The reconstruction of evolutionary pathways and adaptation processes of living organisms is important not only to understand the complicated relationship between the organisms themselves and their surrounding environment, but also in the context of their use as models for bioinspiration, especially in the robotics field. In fact, bioinspired robotics takes the cue from the solutions achieved by living organisms (Whitesides, 2015), which in turn depend on adaptations developed through millions of years of evolution. Understanding the origin and development of certain characters, which are relevant for bioinspiration purpose, is strictly linked to the understanding of the natural history of the organisms. However, the last thirty years of biological research showed that morphological characters only cannot give a comprehensive view on the diversity and evolution of organisms (Schlick-Steiner et al., 2010; Yeates et al., 2011). In fact, the reconstruction of evolutionary processes that led to the diversity patterns we are observing nowadays can be achieved only through the integration of different arrays of data.

In the wide array of attractive living organisms, worms serve as an intriguing source of bioinspiration since examples of controlling movements through the mechanical reactions of fully soft-bodied parts. Consequently, understanding their evolutionary processes has the potential to illustrate how the softness and plasticity characteristic of worms can inspire the fulfilment of fundamental requirements in numerous robotic application fields. In this context, the aim of the project MAPWORMS (Mimicking Adaptations and Plasticity in WORMS) is the integrated study of marine annelids for bioinspiring new soft robotics solutions, focusing on some model worms showing interesting behavioural and anatomical features (Langeneck et al., 2023a). This deliverable is aimed at investigating the diversity of marine annelids occurring along the coasts of Salento in the context of their use as model for bioinspiration and biomimetics in the robotics field; aside from the model species identified by Langeneck et al. (2023a), we decided to extend this characterisation to other groups that are not considered in the project MAPWORMS, but might have interesting traits for other applicative studies, in order to give a baseline on the diversity of marine annelids in the study area.

1.1 INTEGRATIVE TAXONOMY TO UNRAVEL THE DIVERSITY OF ORGANISMS

As stated previously, although the identification of organisms and the assessment of the relationships among them was historically based mainly on their morphological characters, during the last century, research showed that morphological characters alone do not allow to obtain a satisfactory overview of their diversity. In fact, research carried out on protozoans in the 1930s showed that, despite identical morphologies, some alleged species included several lineages that were not able to interbreed (Sonneborn, 1939); soon, this was proved to be true for several multicellular organisms (Mayr, 1942; Knowlton, 1993), leading to the development of the concept of cryptic species, i.e., organisms that are morphologically similar or identical to one another but are genetically distinct, often to the point of

being considered separate species. Thus, morphological characters are usually not enough to discriminate between different cryptic species, more as the consequence of overlapping morphological variability and phenotypic plasticity, i.e. the ability to adapt to different contexts and environments through morphological and developmental changes, rather than due to morphological homogeneity (Langeneck et al., 2020). In several cases, overlooked characters that were considered to show a wide variation within a single species turned out to be good predictors of the differences retrieved using other types of data; in this case the scientific community prefers the use of the term “pseudocryptic species” (Knowlton, 2000; Luttikhuisen & Dekker, 2010), even though the distinction between cryptic and pseudocryptic species is not always straightforward and might depend on which data are used, and on their interpretation (Korshunova et al., 2019). Additional sets of data that, despite the lack of morphological differentiation, allow to discriminate between cryptic species might include reproductive traits and compatibility (Sonneborn, 1939; Teixeira et al., 2022a; Kordbacheh et al., 2023), ultrastructural features (Marques et al., 2007; Zhang et al., 2015), physiology and biochemistry (Montresor et al., 2003; Muangmai et al., 2015; Roma-Marzio et al., 2017), genetics (Grassle & Grassle, 1976; Maltagliati et al., 2001; Nygren & Pleijel, 2011), behaviour (Töpfer-Hofmann et al., 2000; Tan et al., 2010; Cabrol et al., 2015), the presence of symbionts (McGovern & Hellberg, 2003; Prada et al., 2014) and more generally the microbiome associated to the organism (Derycke et al., 2016). The evidence that morphology alone is not able to give us a satisfactory outlook on the diversity of living organisms led to the concept of integrative taxonomy (Schlick-Steiner et al., 2010). In principle, integrative taxonomy should consider all these factors when attempting to correctly unravel the diversity of a group of organisms (Schlick-Steiner et al., 2010; Serra et al., 2020). However, the majority of studies take into account only one or a few of these data types, as two or three lines of evidence are usually enough to obtain a sound distinction between groups of organisms.

Among these lines of evidence, the use of molecular data and, in particular, DNA and protein sequences is the most widespread approach to the study of cryptic and pseudocryptic species. It should be stressed that not all characters employed in the characterisation of organisms have an adaptive meaning; some of them are directly involved in adaptation and selection processes and, as such, might end up being misleading (for instance, in presence of phenotypic plasticity or convergent evolution); other characters are merely retained as a result of casual variation which is not counter-selected by the environment, and is fixed by demographic phenomena, such as bottlenecks, founder effects and genetic drift. This is, of course, true also for molecular data: some genes have a direct role in adaptive mechanisms and should be evaluated in this light, taking into account the possibility of independent evolution of similarities; however, other genes are considered as neutral markers, as they are not directly subject to natural selection, either because they do not code for anything, or because the protein or structural RNA they code for works in the same exact way in all living organisms and the only changes allowed are those not impairing its

functioning. The evolution of neutral molecular markers is driven by casual mutations which accumulate through time; for this reason, mutations in neutral markers can be considered (albeit with some caution) as a proxy of the time elapsed since the separation between two groups of organisms. The first studies using molecular data to disentangle the diversity of organisms employed either the number and shape of chromosomes (karyotypes: Cognetti-Varriale, 1967; Curini-Galletti et al., 1991) or the migration pattern of isoforms of specific enzymes isolated from the tissue of the organism of interest (alloenzymes: Grassle & Grassle, 1976; Maltagliati et al., 2000). Karyotypes can be considered as borderline between morphological and molecular characters, as they can be easily visualised on microscope slides, and what is analysed is, ultimately, their shape and number; since, generally speaking, organisms with a different number of chromosomes are usually assumed to be at least partially inter-sterile, chromosomes are considered a proxy of reproductive separation rather than of elapsed time, and their use to identify cryptic species follows Mayr's (1942) species concept. While in plant taxonomy karyotypes are still widely used, due to the ease in obtaining them from seedlings, obtaining karyotypes from animals is a tedious process and, despite the first promising results, this technique was soon abandoned in favour of the alloenzymes. Alloenzymes, on their hand, cannot be considered as neutral markers, as they are based on the migration pattern of different isoforms of functional proteins, which depends on adaptations to environmental stressors and constraints, sometimes through the differential expression of genes. As such, the pattern retrieved using this kind of markers might not correspond to the one obtained through neutral markers and several of these early studies tend to give inaccurate results if compared with more modern techniques (Langeneck et al., 2020). At the same time, the constraints on protein functional aspects reduce the variability of alloenzymes, which tend to underestimate the differences among closely related organisms (Oliver et al., 2010).

Due to the development of reliable DNA sequencing techniques and the steadfast decrease in their cost, between the end of the 1990s and the beginning of the 2000s the bulk of the research shifted from the technically demanding and time-consuming karyotypes and alloenzymes to the sequencing of DNA fragments corresponding to specific genes. An evident downside of DNA sequencing is represented by the fact that, unlike alloenzymes, it does not give any information about gene expression, and is therefore scarcely suitable for the study of adaptive mechanisms, especially at the microevolutionary level. However, this limitation represents an evident strength when it comes to separate adaptive and neutral features, as DNA sequencing is mostly taking into account the neutral characters. While, technically speaking, any fragment of genomic DNA could be amplified and sequenced, the choice of the markers employed depends on two factors, namely, the availability of sequences on public databases (which are fundamental to compare results) and the mutation rate. Typically, the mitochondrial genome has a mutation rate which is approximately four times that of the nuclear genome, and non-coding genes are obviously subject to fewer constraints with respect to coding ones, as all mutations impairing the functionality of

a coding sequence would be counter-selected and have a really low likelihood to be fixed at population level. For this reason, non-coding mitochondrial genes are usually employed for population studies within a single species; coding mitochondrial genes and non-coding nuclear genes are versatile enough to be successfully used for both populations studies and the identification of cryptic and pseudocryptic species, but are weak for the reconstruction of phylogenetic relationships; lastly, coding nuclear genes usually do not give enough resolution to discriminate between closely related species, but their lower mutation rates allow sounder reconstructions of the phylogenetic relationships within a group. In particular, a ~650 bp fragment of the mitochondrial gene coding for the subunit I of the cytochrome c oxidase (COI), an enzyme belonging to the mitochondrial respiratory chain, became the standard sequence for the characterisation and identification of animal species (Folmer et al., 1994; Hebert et al., 2003). Hebert et al. (2003) suggested that COI sequences can be employed as a "barcode" for a ready and reliable identification of organisms, and the term "barcoding" quickly became synonymous with the delineation and identification of species through molecular markers. COI was quickly complemented or replaced with other molecular markers, depending on how easy its amplification was. In particular, the amplification of mitochondrial genes in plants is usually very difficult and molecular studies are mostly based on plastidial genes, while in several groups of animals COI amplification might be difficult, and this marker was paired with the use of the mitochondrial genes coding for ribosomal RNA (12S rRNA and 16S rRNA) as well as other mitochondrial genes coding for the respiratory chain (as *cytB*) or nuclear non-coding fragments (as the ITS1 and ITS2 regions of the ribosomal cistron). It is worth noting that the identification of organisms through DNA barcoding strongly depends on the availability of reliable barcode libraries, either based on the results of integrative taxonomy studies, or on studies characterising the entire assemblages occurring in a specific habitat/geographical area (Lobo et al., 2016; Weigand et al., 2019); especially this latter kind of study is subject to either processing errors, leading to poor quality data, or identification mistakes that might further propagate to following studies, so barcode libraries should be updated, corrected, and approached critically (Cheng et al., 2023). Notwithstanding these limitations, barcode libraries still represent a powerful tool for both a correct interpretation of sequence data, and for practical applications allowed by second- and third-generation sequencing techniques.

Until recently, the majority of DNA sequencing was based on the technique developed by Sanger et al. (1977), which is still widely used to obtain barcoding data. This technique is reliable and cheap, but it has the downside of allowing the sequencing of only one gene at a time. The recent development of next-generation sequencing technologies, such as Illumina, pyrosequencing and Nanopore, allowed to either sequence multiple genes for the same organism (with the possibility of potentially reconstruct its entire genome), sequence the entire transcriptome of an organism (allowing to reconstruct its gene expression), or sequence the same genes for a multitude of organisms (with the possibility to reconstruct the microbiome occurring on a surface, or within a larger organism, or to give an insight into the

structure of a community based on the DNA traces occurring in the environment - environmental DNA, or eDNA). These exciting potentialities given by second- and third-generation sequencing technologies, however, are made possible only by the presence of barcoding libraries and genetic databases, which are still largely based on Sanger sequencing, and this is particularly true when using eDNA to reconstruct the diversity and structure of an assemblage.

1.2 INTEGRATIVE TAXONOMY TO UNRAVEL THE DIVERSITY OF MARINE ANNELIDS

Even though cryptic and pseudocryptic species are widespread in all animal groups, marine annelids represent a particularly interesting group for integrative taxonomy studies. Despite their prevalence in all benthic marine environments, where they are often the most abundant and most diverse group, until recently marine annelids were considered as a group characterised by a relatively low species diversity, including mostly cosmopolitan species, and thus providing scarce biogeographical information (Ekman, 1953). This discrepancy towards all other invertebrate groups is mostly due to Pierre Fauvel (1866-1958), the most pre-eminent annelidologist of the XX Century, who put most of the taxa described in the XIX Century into synonymy with a few cosmopolitan species (Fauvel, 1914; 1923; 1927). Fauvel's view remained unchallenged until the 1980s, when polychaetological research started to know a new flourishing, and the hypothesis of a few, cosmopolitan species was considered unlikely, also in the light of the biogeographical patterns detected in other marine invertebrates (Fauchald, 1984). Recent research showed that cryptic and pseudocryptic species are widespread in marine annelids (Nygren, 2014), and that true cosmopolitan species, or species with very wide distribution, are scarce, and, usually, restricted to bathyal and abyssal environments (Ahrens et al., 2013; Eilertsen et al., 2018). Nonetheless, several annelid species are still considered cosmopolitan or with a very wide distribution, and reported very far from their type locality, from an extremely wide bathymetric distribution, or from very different environments. It is therefore increasingly clear that, even if Fauvel's view is not followed anymore in annelidological research, we are still greatly underestimating the actual diversity of several annelid groups, and what we are considering as a single species is often likely to be a species complex or even a complex of species complexes.

An accurate description of the diversity of the life on earth is the main reason to study cryptic and pseudocryptic species. However, there are also more practical reasons to disentangle the diversity of organisms, and understand its origins and relationships. Different species revealed by molecular data might have different ecological traits and might respond in different ways to environmental and anthropogenic pressures; the correct identification of species is important not only for the sake of their conservation, but also to plan sustainable management strategies for species representing natural resources with an economic value (Arias & Paxton, 2015; Healey et al., 2018) or, on the opposite, to effectively manage pest species (Prasanna et al., 2015; Jiu et al., 2017). As regards marine annelids, several species are considered bioindicators and, together with other benthic invertebrates, are commonly

used in the evaluation of the environmental status of marine environments (Borja et al., 2000; Simboura & Zenetos, 2002; Bald et al., 2005). These indices are based on the assignation of all species to sensitivity categories; however, different cryptic or pseudocryptic species originally identified as a single species might be characterised by different sensitivity towards environmental stressors, and the missed discrimination between them might end up confusing the results of environmental quality indices, hindering or delaying mitigation actions and indirectly decreasing the quality of life of the human population living in the surrounding area. Apparently identical cryptic species might occur in areas outside their natural distribution as non-indigenous species, and their missed detection, or the erroneous identification of their origin and their environmental sensitivities, might end up delaying extirpation and mitigation measures (Viard et al., 2019; Golo et al., 2023). Lastly, discriminating between different cryptic species is crucial for their use as models, either for developmental biology (Caputi et al., 2007; Teixeira et al., 2022a) or for bioinspiration in robotics (Schulze & Kawachi, 2021). In fact, morphologically similar species can occur in different environments and have experienced different adaptation processes, which can lead to reproductive, physiological, behavioural, and structural divergence that should be taken into account when those taxa are considered as suitable model species for bioinspiration.

This deliverable is ideally conceived as the follow-up to Deliverable 2.1 (Langeneck et al., 2023a), which included an updated checklist of the marine annelids occurring along the Salento Peninsula. The morphological identification of the species found in Deliverable 2.1 is here complemented by molecular data, with the aim to give a further insight into the diversity of this group in the study area. In particular, the analysis concentrated on all species that have been characterised through micro-CT scans for further potential application as models for soft robots, as well as non-indigenous species, whose spread should be monitored in compliance with the current EU legislation on environmental protection, and species that are known or strongly suspected to be species complexes.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 SAMPLE COLLECTION AND PRESERVATION

The majority of the samples obtained during the first two years of the MAPWORMS project were preserved either in 96% ethanol, which is optimal for DNA preservation, or in 70% ethanol, which is sub-optimal but still allows the extraction of good quality DNA if the processing of samples is not delayed. Whenever possible, the samples were preserved at low temperatures, either in a fridge (4 °C) or in a freezer (-20 °C) to limit DNA degradation. Among the >800 samples available for genetic analyses, we chose the individuals to characterise based on the presence of relevant features from a bioinspired modelling point of view. In agreement with the parameters established in Deliverable 2.1 (Langeneck et al., 2023a), potential model species (marked as potential models in Table 1) were chosen based on both the presence of interesting anatomical features for the general purpose of the project MAPWORMS, and the common occurrence in shallow environments, that makes their

finding relatively easy and predictable. More generally, we aimed at covering all families reported in the checklist, or, at least, all those for which ethanol-preserved material was available. The number of species assayed for each family depended on the diversity of the available material, but in general we tried to include several species for each annelid family in order to give a general baseline on the diversity of this group along the Salento Peninsula.

A small tissue fragment (1 mm³ or less) was cut off from the individual, taking care not to damage or remove any diagnostic feature, and employed for DNA extraction. Total genomic DNA was extracted using the salting-out protocol (Aljanabi & Martínez, 1997) with the modifications detailed in Furfaro et al. (2022). After drying up to at least one hour at 37 °C to remove any trace of ethanol, tissue fragments were incubated overnight at 55-60 °C with 435 µl of a cell lysis buffer (0.5% of Tris HCl [pH 8], 20% EDTA 0.5 M [pH 8], 0.2% NaCl 5M, 10% SDS 10% and 63% ultrapure water) and 15 µl of proteinase K to obtain a lysate. The lysate was subsequently centrifuged at 13200 g for 10 minutes, and 400 µl of the supernatant were transferred to another set of microcentrifuge tubes. 160 µl of 5M NaCl were added to the supernatant, and the tubes were again centrifuged at 13200 g for 10 minutes to precipitate all macromolecules that are not nucleic acids. 500 µl of the supernatant were transferred to a third set of microcentrifuge tubes, and 500 µl of absolute isopropanol at -20 °C were added. The tubes were centrifuged at 13200 g for 10 minutes to precipitate DNA on the bottom of the tubes. The supernatant was then discarded and replaced with 1 ml of 80% ethanol at room temperature and centrifuged at 13200 g for 10 minutes to remove any residual of other macromolecules. The supernatant was discarded, and the samples were left to dry at 37 °C for at least one hour to remove all ethanol. The extracted genomic DNA was resuspended in 150 µl of ultrapure water and stored at -20 °C.

2.2 GENETIC CHARACTERIZATION

For the genetic characterisation we chose two mitochondrial markers that are commonly employed in DNA barcoding of marine invertebrates, namely a ~620 bp fragment of the COI and a ~470-490 bp fragment of the 16S rDNA. The choice of the markers was mainly due to the availability of sequences to be compared in public databases; while COI is generally considered the marker of choice for barcoding studies, its amplification is challenging in several annelid families (Sun et al., 2012; Brasier et al., 2016; Bonifácio et al., 2020), for this reason we decided to also amplify the comparatively easier 16S, in particular for those species for which COI amplification turned out to be impossible. COI amplification was obtained mainly with the annelid-specific primers POLYLCO (5'-GAYTAT-WTCAACAAATCATAAAGATATTGG-3') and POLYHCO (5'-TAMACTTCWGGGTGACCAAAR-AATCA-3') (Carr et al., 2011) and the universal degenerate primers optimised for marine invertebrates jGLCO1490 (5'-TITCIACIAAYCAYAARGAYATTGG-3') and jGH2198 (5'-TAIACYTCIGGRTGICCRARAAYCA-3') (Geller et al., 2013). The original universal primers designed by Folmer et al. (1994), LCO1490 (5'-GGTCAACAAATCATAAAGATATTGG-3') and HCO2198 (5'-TGATTTTTGGTCACCCTGAAGTTA-3') gave a much lower amplification

success rate with respect to the degenerate versions, and after a few preliminary trials were mostly abandoned. 16S amplification was obtained with the primer pair 16SL (5'-CGCCTGTTAACAAAACAT-3') and H3080 (5'-CCGGTCTGAACTCAGATCACGT-3') (Palumbi et al., 1991). PCR amplifications were carried out in a 20 µl volume, using 4 µL of FIRE-Pol® Master Mix (Solis BioDyne), 0.1 µM of each primer and 1 µL of template DNA. For 16S rDNA the PCR profile was set as follows: initial denaturing step at 94 °C for 4 min, 35 cycles of denaturing at 94 °C for 30 s, annealing at 50 °C for 30 s, and extending at 72 °C for 45 s, with a final extending step at 72 °C for 7 min. For COI, annealing temperature was set at 45 °C and the PCR profile included 40 cycles. A negative control was included in each reaction. PCR products were sent to Macrogen Europe for purification and sequencing.

Electropherograms obtained from Macrogen Europe as the results of the sequencing were manually edited with the open source software Chromas 2.6.6. (Technelysium Ltd) to check the quality of the sequence and remove low quality regions. The resulting sequences were compared with those available in public repositories. In particular, COI sequences were compared with sequences deposited in GenBank (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/>) through the Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST: <https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>) and with sequences deposited in Barcode of Life Data System v4 (BOLD Systems: <https://www.boldsystems.org/>) through the Identification Engine tool (https://www.boldsystems.org/index.php/IDS_IdentificationRequest). The comparison with the two databases was driven by the fact that the overlap between them is not complete, especially as regards the more recent sequences; moreover, GenBank allows to compare the query sequence only with published entries, while BOLD Systems allows a comparison with private records, even if the sequence and its metadata are not available. Since BOLD Systems allows a comparison only between COI sequences, 16S sequences were only compared with those available in GenBank.

3 RESULTS

Total genomic DNA was extracted from 422 individuals belonging to 202 morphospecies; for 143 species we were able to obtain good quality sequences of at least one of the two employed molecular markers, while for the remaining 78 species, even when PCRs gave amplification success, the sequence was not readable or of poor quality (Table 1). Sequencing success of the amplified bands ranged between 64.6 and 85.4% per plate (average value: $74.8 \pm 8.8\%$). The amplification success rate varied between different annelid families; in fact, for some families (e.g., Nereididae, Terebellidae) we were able to obtain sequences for all the morphospecies identified, even though not for all individuals, while for some families (e.g., Capitellidae, Cirratulidae) both amplification and sequencing gave very low success. This is unfortunately true also for some poorly known families including a very small number of Mediterranean species (e.g., Acrocirridae, Arenicolidae), even if other families characterised by limited diversity (e.g., Paralacydoniidae, Pilargidae) gave a very high amplification and sequencing success. The overall amplification success was

comparable for the two markers and the three primer pairs (jGLCO1490-jGHCO2148: $43.74 \pm 20.06\%$, N= 43; POLYLCO-POLYHCO: $40.76 \pm 25.11\%$, N= 28; 16SL-H3080: $44.34 \pm 18.95\%$, N= 32) even though the two primer pairs employed for COI amplification showed strong differences in amplification success between different families (e.g., jGLCO1490-jGHCO2148 was successful on Syllidae and Nereididae, but not on Terebellidae and Phyllodocidae, and POLYLCO-POLYHCO was successful on Terebellidae and Phyllodocidae, but not on Syllidae and Nereididae). All sequences obtained were uploaded to BOLD within the project "MAPWORMS – Mimicking Adaptations and Plasticity in WORMS", under embargo until the planned publication of the checklist, expected for the year 2025.

Table 1. LIST OF THE MARINE ANNELID SPECIES EXAMINED FROM THE MOLECULAR POINT OF VIEW, WITH NUMBER OF INDIVIDUALS FOR WHICH DNA EXTRACTION AND AMPLIFICATION WAS ATTEMPTED (N° OF INDIVIDUALS), SEQUENCING SUCCESS, NUMBER OF LINEAGES RETRIEVED DURING THIS STUDY (PRESENT DATA) AND OVERALL NUMBER OF LINEAGES KNOWN FROM THE PRESENT DATA MERGED WITH THOSE AVAILABLE ON GENBANK. Y= YES; N= NO.

Family	Species	N° of individuals	Amplification success	N° of lineages (N)	N° of lineages (G)
Acrocirridae	<i>Macrochaeta clavicornis</i> (M. Sars, 1835)	1	N		
Amphinomidae	<i>Cryptonome conclava</i> Borda, Kudenov, Bienhold & Rouse, 2012	1	Y	1	1
Amphinomidae	<i>Euphosine foliosa</i> Audouin & Milne-Edwards, 1833	2	Y	1	1
Amphinomidae	<i>Eurythoe complanata</i> (Pallas, 1766)	6	Y	1	6
Aphroditidae	<i>Laetmonice hystrix</i> (Savigny in Lamarck, 1818)	1	Y	1	1
Aphroditidae	<i>Pontogenia chrysocoma</i> (Baird, 1865)	1	Y	1	1
Arenicolidae	<i>Abarenicola claparedi</i> (Levinsen, 1884)	2	N		
Aspidosiphonidae	<i>Aspidosiphon muelleri</i> Diesing, 1851	3	Y	2	2
Bonelliidae	<i>Bonellia viridis</i> Rolando, 1821	3	Y	1	2
Capitellidae	<i>Capitella teleta</i> Blake, Grassle & Eckelbarger, 2009	2	N		
Capitellidae	<i>Dasybranchus caducus</i> (Grube, 1846)	1	N	1	1
Capitellidae	<i>Dasybranchus gajolae</i> Eisig, 1887	2	Y	1	1
Capitellidae	<i>Notomastus latericeus</i> Sars, 1851	2	N		
Capitellidae	<i>Pseudoleiocapitella fauveli</i> Harmelin, 1964	1	N		
Chrysopetalidae	<i>Arichlidon reyssi</i> (Katzmann, Laubier & Ramos, 1974)	2	N		
Chrysopetalidae	<i>Chrysopetalum debile</i> (Grube, 1855)	2	Y	1	1
Chrysopetalidae	<i>Paleanotus chrysolepis</i> Schmarda, 1861	1	Y	1	1
Cirratulidae	<i>Caulleriella bioculata</i> (Keferstein, 1862)	2	N		
Cirratulidae	<i>Caulleriella</i> sp. 1	1	N		
Cirratulidae	<i>Caulleriella</i> sp. 2	2	N		
Cirratulidae	<i>Dodecaceria</i> sp.	3	N		
Cirratulidae	<i>Fauvelicirratulus dollfusi</i> (Fauvel, 1928)	1	N		

Family	Species	N° of individuals	Amplification success	N° of lineages (N)	N° of lineages (G)
Dorvilleidae	<i>Dorvillea rubrovittata</i> (Grube, 1855)	2	Y	1	2
Dorvilleidae	<i>Dorvillea similis</i> (Crossland, 1924)	5	Y	2	5
Dorvilleidae	<i>Dorvillea</i> sp. 1	1	Y	1	1
Dorvilleidae	<i>Ophryotrocha</i> sp. 1	2	Y	1	1
Dorvilleidae	<i>Parougia eliasoni</i> (Oug, 1978)	2	Y	1	1
Dorvilleidae	<i>Pettiboneia urciensis</i> Campoy & San Martin, 1980	2	N		
Dorvilleidae	<i>Protodorvillea artemidis</i> Munari & Ebbe, 2019	1	N		
Dorvilleidae	<i>Protodorvillea kefersteini</i> (McIntosh, 1869)	3	Y		
Dorvilleidae	<i>Schistomeringos rudolphi</i> (Delle Chiaje, 1828)	2	Y	1	1
Eunicidae	<i>Eunice roussaei</i> Quatrefages, 1866	2	N		
Eunicidae	<i>Eunice schizobranchia</i> Claparède, 1870	1	Y	1	1
Eunicidae	<i>Eunice vittata</i> (Delle Chiaje, 1828)	1	N		
Eunicidae	<i>Leodice</i> aff. <i>harassii</i> (Audouin & Milne-Edwards, 1833)	1	Y	1	1
Eunicidae	<i>Leodice harassii</i> (Audouin & Milne-Edwards, 1833)	1	Y	1	1
Eunicidae	<i>Leodice torquata</i> (Quatrefages, 1866)	2	N		
Eunicidae	<i>Lysidice ninetta</i> Audouin & Milne-Edwards, 1833	1	N		
Eunicidae	<i>Marphysa</i> aff. <i>adenensis</i> Gravier, 1900	1	Y	1	1
Eunicidae	<i>Marphysa chirigota</i> Martin, Gil & Zanol, 2020	3	Y	2	2
Eunicidae	<i>Marphysa sanguinea</i> (Montagu, 1813)	3	Y	1	3
Eunicidae	<i>Palola siciliensis</i> (Grube, 1840)	5	Y	1	1
Eunicidae	<i>Palola valida</i> (Gravier, 1900)	1	Y	1	3
Flabelligeridae	<i>Diplocirrus glaucus</i> (Malmgren, 1867)	1	Y	1	1
Flabelligeridae	<i>Flabelligera affinis</i> M. Sars, 1829	1	Y	1	1
Flabelligeridae	<i>Piromis eruca</i> (Claparède, 1869)	1	N		
Flabelligeridae	<i>Stylarioides monilliferus</i> Delle Chiaje, 1841	1	Y	1	1

Family	Species	N° of individuals	Amplification success	N° of lineages (N)	N° of lineages (G)
Glyceridae	<i>Glycera alba</i> (O. F. Müller, 1776)	2	Y	1	2
Glyceridae	<i>Glycera tessellata</i> Grube, 1863	2	Y	1	1
Glyceridae	<i>Glycera tridactyla</i> Schmarda, 1861	1	N		
Goniadidae	<i>Glycinde nordmanni</i> (Malmgren, 1866)	1	Y	1	1
Goniadidae	<i>Goniada emerita</i> Audouin & Milne Edwards, 1833/ <i>Goniada hexadentes</i> Böggemann & Eibye-Jacobsen, 2002	2	Y	1	1
Hesionidae	<i>Amphiduros fuscescens</i> (Marenzeller, 1875)	1	Y	1	2
Hesionidae	<i>Gyptis propinqua</i> Marion & Bobretzky, 1875	1	Y	1	2
Hesionidae	<i>Hesiospina aurantiaca</i> (M. Sars, 1862)	1	Y	1	2
Hesionidae	<i>Leocrates claparedii</i> (Costa in Claparède, 1868)	1	Y	1	1
Lacydoniidae	<i>Lacydonia miranda</i> Marion, 1874	2	N		
Lumbrineridae	<i>Gallardoneris nonatoi</i> (Ramos, 1976)	1	N		
Lumbrineridae	<i>Lumbrinerides amoureuxi</i> Miura, 1981	1	Y	1	1
Lumbrineridae	<i>Lumbrineris aniara</i> Fauchald, 1974	1	Y	1	1
Lumbrineridae	<i>Lumbrineris</i> cf. <i>lusitanica</i> Martins, Carrera-Parra, Quintino & Rodrigues, 2012	1	N		
Lumbrineridae	<i>Lumbrineris coccinea</i> (Renier, 1804)	1	Y	1	1
Lumbrineridae	<i>Lumbrineris latreilli</i> Audouin & Milne Edwards, 1833	7	Y	3	3
Lumbrineridae	<i>Lumbrineris longipodiata</i> Cantone, 1990	1	N		
Lumbrineridae	<i>Lumbrineris perkinsi</i> Carrera-Parra, 2001	2	Y	1	1
Lumbrineridae	<i>Scoletoma</i> cf. <i>fragilis</i> (O. F. Müller, 1776)	1	Y	1	1
Magelonidae	<i>Magelona equilamellae</i> Harmelin, 1964	1	Y	1	1
Nephtyidae	<i>Micronephthys longicornis</i> (Perejaslvtseva, 1891)	1	N		
Nephtyidae	<i>Nephtys sinopensis</i> Kuş, Kurt & Çınar, 2021	1	N		
Nereididae	<i>Composetia costae</i> (Grube, 1840)	1	Y	1	1
Nereididae	<i>Neanthes nubila</i> (Savigny, 1822)	1	Y	1	1

Family	Species	N° of individuals	Amplification success	N° of lineages (N)	N° of lineages (G)
Nereididae	<i>Neanthes</i> sp. 1	1	Y	1	1
Nereididae	<i>Nereis</i> cf. <i>agulhana</i> Day, 1963	2	Y	1	1
Nereididae	<i>Perinereis cultrifera</i> (Grube, 1840)	12	Y	5	13
Nereididae	<i>Perinereis rullieri</i> Pilato, 1974	3	Y	2	6
Nereididae	<i>Pseudonereis anomala</i> Gravier, 1899	3	Y	1	1
Oeononidae	<i>Arabella</i> cf. <i>longicirrata</i> Hartmann-Schröder, 1979	1	Y	1	1
Oeononidae	<i>Arabella geniculata</i> (Claparède, 1868)	1	N		
Oeononidae	<i>Drilonereis</i> cf. <i>macrocephala</i> Saint-Joseph, 1888	2	Y	1	1
Oeononidae	<i>Drilonereis filum</i> (Claparède, 1868)	1	N		
Oeononidae	<i>Halla parthenopeia</i> (Delle Chiaje, 1828)	1	Y	1	1
Oeononidae	<i>Labrorostratus</i> sp.	1	Y	1	1
Onuphidae	<i>Aponuphis bilineata</i> (Baird, 1870)	3	Y	1	3
Opheliidae	<i>Ophelia amoureuksi</i> Bellan & Costa, 1988	1	Y	1	1
Opheliidae	<i>Ophelia</i> sp. 1	1	Y	1	1
Opheliidae	<i>Polyopthalmus pictus</i> (Dujardin, 1839)	18	Y	3	6
Orbiniidae	<i>Gesaschroederella laubieri</i> (Badalamenti & Castelli, 1991)	1	Y	1	1
Orbiniidae	<i>Naineris laevigata</i> (Grube, 1855)	2	Y	2	2
Orbiniidae	<i>Naineris setosa</i> (Verrill, 1900)	2	Y	1	3
Orbiniidae	<i>Scoloplos</i> sp.	1	Y	1	1
Orbiniidae	<i>Scoloplos typicus</i> (Eisig, 1914)	1	Y	1	1
Oweniidae	<i>Galathowenia oculata</i> (Zachs, 1923)	1	N		
Oweniidae	<i>Myriochele danielsseni</i> (Hansen, 1878)	1	Y	1	1
Oweniidae	<i>Owenia fusiformis</i> Delle Chiaje, 1844	1	Y	1	5
Paralacydoniidae	<i>Paralacydonia paradoxa</i> Fauvel, 1913	1	Y	1	1
Paraonidae	<i>Aricidea bansei</i> Laubier & Ramos, 1974	1	N		

Family	Species	N° of individuals	Amplification success	N° of lineages (N)	N° of lineages (G)
Paraonidae	<i>Aricidea</i> cf. <i>claudiae</i> Laubier, 1967	1	Y	1	2
Paraonidae	<i>Aricidea katzmanni</i> Erdoğan-Dereli & Çınar, 2020	5	Y	1	2
Paraonidae	<i>Cirrophorus nikebianchii</i> Langeneck, Barbieri, Maltagliati & Castelli, 2017	2	Y	1	1
Paraonidae	<i>Paradoneis ilvana</i> Castelli, 1985	2	Y	1	3
Phascolosomatidae	<i>Phascolosoma stephensoni</i> Stephen, 1942/ <i>Phascolosoma</i> cf. <i>granulatum</i> Leuckart, 1828	8	Y	1	1
Phyllodocidae	<i>Eumida</i> aff. <i>ockelmanni</i> Eibye-Jacobsen, 1987	1	Y	1	1
Phyllodocidae	<i>Eumida langenecki</i> Teixeira, Vieira, Ravara, Costa & Nygren, 2022	1	Y	1	2
Phyllodocidae	<i>Eumida</i> sp. 1	3	Y	1	1
Phyllodocidae	<i>Nereiphylla</i> cf. <i>lugens</i> (Ehlers, 1864)	2	Y	1	1
Phyllodocidae	<i>Notophyllum foliosum</i> (Sars, 1835)	2	Y	1	3
Phyllodocidae	<i>Phyllodoce madeirensis</i> Langerhans, 1880	1	N		
Phyllodocidae	<i>Protomystides bidentata</i> (Langerhans, 1880)	3	Y	2	2
Phyllodocidae	<i>Protomystides bilineata</i> La Greca, 1946	1	N		
Phyllodocidae	<i>Pseudomystides limbata limbata</i> (Saint-Joseph, 1888)	1	Y	1	2
Phyllodocidae	<i>Pseudomystides limbata nigrolineata</i> (Rioja, 1925)	1	Y	1	1
Phyllodocidae	<i>Pterocirrus macroceros</i> (Grube, 1860)	1	Y	1	4
Pilargidae	<i>Sigambra tentaculata</i> (Treadwell, 1941)	1	Y	1	1
Polynoidae	<i>Harmothoe</i> cf. <i>fraserthomsoni</i> McIntosh, 1897	1	N		
Polynoidae	<i>Harmothoe extenuata</i> (Grube, 1840)	1	Y	1	1
Polynoidae	<i>Lepidonotus clava</i> (Montagu, 1808)	1	Y	1	2
Polynoidae	<i>Lepidonotus tenuisetosus</i> (Gravier, 1902)	2	Y	1	1
Polynoidae	<i>Malmgrenia lunulata</i> (Delle Chiaje, 1830)	1	N		
Polynoidae	<i>Subadyte pellucida</i> (Ehlers, 1864)	4	Y	1	1

Family	Species	N° of individuals	Amplification success	N° of lineages (N)	N° of lineages (G)
Sabellidae	<i>Acromegalomma adriaticum</i> (Giangrande, Caruso, Mikac & Lucciano, 2015)	1	N		
Sabellidae	<i>Acromegalomma lanigerum</i> (Grube, 1846)	1	Y	1	1
Sabellidae	<i>Acromegalomma longoventrale</i> (Giangrande, Caruso, Mikac & Lucciano, 2015)	1	Y	1	1
Sabellidae	<i>Amphiglena mediterranea</i> (Leydig, 1851)	9	Y	7	18
Sabellidae	<i>Bispira mariae</i> Lo Bianco, 1893	1	Y	1	1
Sabellidae	<i>Bispira</i> sp. 1	1	Y	1	1
Sabellidae	<i>Bispira viola</i> (Grube, 1863)	6	Y	1	1
Sabellidae	<i>Branchiomma bairdi</i> (McIntosh, 1885)	2	N		
Sabellidae	<i>Branchiomma boholense</i> (Grube, 1878)	4	Y	1	1
Sabellidae	<i>Branchiomma bombyx</i> (Dalyell, 1853)	1	Y	1	2
Sabellidae	<i>Branchiomma luctuosum</i> (Grube, 1870)	2	Y	1	1
Sabellidae	<i>Dialychone acustica</i> Claparède, 1868	1	Y	1	1
Sabellidae	<i>Dialychone collaris</i> (Langerhans, 1880)	2	Y	1	1
Sabellidae	<i>Dialychone dunerificta</i> (Tovar-Hernandez, Giangrande & Lucciano, 2007)	1	Y	1	1
Sabellidae	<i>Euchone</i> cf. <i>southerni</i> Banse, 1970	1	N		
Sabellidae	<i>Euchone pararosea</i> Giangrande & Lucciano, 2006	1	N		
Sabellidae	<i>Euchone pseudolimnicola</i> Giangrande & Lucciano, 2006	1	Y	1	1
Sabellidae	<i>Euchone rosea</i> Langerhans, 1884	1	N		
Sabellidae	<i>Hypsicomus</i> cf. <i>caecus</i> Iroso, 1921	1	Y		
Sabellidae	<i>Hypsicomus styphophthalmos</i> (Grube, 1863)	1	N		
Sabellidae	<i>Jasmineira elegans</i> Saint-Joseph, 1894	1	Y	1	1
Sabellidae	<i>Myxicola</i> cf. <i>parasites</i> Quatrefages, 1866	8	Y	2	2
Sabellidae	<i>Myxicola cosentini</i> Putignano, Gravili & Giangrande, 2023	4	Y	1	1
Sabellidae	<i>Myxicola giuliae</i> Putignano, Gravili & Giangrande, 2023	5	Y	1	1

Family	Species	N° of individuals	Amplification success	N° of lineages (N)	N° of lineages (G)
Sabellidae	<i>Myxicola cataldoi</i> Putignano, Gravili & Gian-grande, 2023/ <i>Myxicola infundibulum</i> (Montagu, 1808)	5	Y	1	1
Sabellidae	<i>Myxicola polychroma</i> Darbyshire, 2023	1	Y	1	1
Sabellidae	<i>Myxicola</i> sp. 1	1	N		
Sabellidae	<i>Myxicola</i> sp. 2	1	Y	1	1
Sabellidae	<i>Myxicola</i> sp. 3	5	Y	1	1
Sabellidae	<i>Myxicola</i> sp. 4	5	Y	1	1
Sabellidae	<i>Perkinsiana</i> sp. 1	1	Y	1	1
Sabellidae	<i>Pseudobranchiomma</i> sp.	1	N		
Sabellidae	<i>Pseudopotamilla saxicava</i> (Quatrefages, 1866)	5	Y	3	4
Sabellidae	<i>Sabella pavonina</i> Savigny, 1822	3	Y	1	1
Sabellidae	<i>Sabella spallanzanii</i> (Gmelin, 1791)/ <i>Sabella discifera</i> Grube, 1863	3	Y	1	1
Scalibregmatidae	<i>Asclerocheilus intermedius</i> (Saint-Joseph, 1894)	3	Y	2	2
Scalibregmatidae	<i>Axiokebuita</i> sp. 1	1	Y	1	1
Scalibregmatidae	<i>Hyboscolex</i> sp.	1	Y	1	1
Scalibregmatidae	<i>Sclerocheilus minutus</i> Grube, 1863	3	Y	2	4
Serpulidae	<i>Protula</i> sp. 1	2	N		
Sigalionidae	<i>Pelogenia arenosa</i> (Delle Chiaje, 1830)	1	N		
Sigalionidae	<i>Pholoe inornata</i> Johnston, 1839	1	Y	1	1
Sigalionidae	<i>Sthenelais boa</i> (Johnston, 1833)	1	N		
Sphaerodoridae	<i>Sphaerodoridium minutum</i> (Webster & Bnedict, 1887)	1	N		
Sphaerodoridae	<i>Sphaerodorum cantonei</i> (Mollica, 1994)	1	N		
Spionidae	<i>Aonides oxycephala</i> (Sars, 1862)	2	Y	1	2
Spionidae	<i>Aurospio banyulensis</i> (Laubier, 1966)	1	N		
Spionidae	<i>Boccardia</i> cf. <i>semibranchiata</i> Guérin, 1990	2	N		

Family	Species	N° of individuals	Amplification success	N° of lineages (N)	N° of lineages (G)
Spionidae	<i>Laonice mediterranea</i> Sikorski, Nygren & Rou-sou, 2021	2	Y		
Spionidae	<i>Polydora</i> sp.	1	N		
Spionidae	<i>Prionospio depauperata</i> Imajima, 1990	3	Y	1	2
Syllidae	<i>Amblyosyllis lineata</i> Grube, 1863	1	Y	1	1
Syllidae	<i>Brevicirrosyllis weismanni</i> (Langerhans, 1879)	1	N		
Syllidae	<i>Dioplosyllis cirrosa</i> Gidholm, 1962	1	Y	1	1
Syllidae	<i>Eusyllis lamelligera</i> Marion & Bobretzky, 1875	1	Y	1	1
Syllidae	<i>Haplosyllis granulosa</i> (Lattig, San Martín & Martín, 2007)	1	Y	1	1
Syllidae	<i>Haplosyllis spongicola</i> (Grube, 1855)	3	Y	1	1
Syllidae	<i>Myrianida rubropunctata</i> (Grube, 1860)	1	Y	1	1
Syllidae	<i>Odontosyllis ctenostoma</i> Claparède, 1868	1	Y	1	1
Syllidae	<i>Odontosyllis fulgurans</i> (Audouin & Milne-Edwards, 1833)	1	Y	1	1
Syllidae	<i>Odontosyllis gibba</i> Claparède, 1863	1	N		
Syllidae	<i>Opisthodontia longocirrata</i> (Saint-Joseph, 1887)	1	N		
Syllidae	<i>Opisthodontia serratisetosa</i> (López, San Martín & Jiménez, 1997)	1	N		
Syllidae	<i>Paraehlersia</i> sp. 1	1	N		
Syllidae	<i>Perkinsyllis anophthalma</i> (Capaccioni & San Martín, 1990)	1	Y	1	1
Syllidae	<i>Syllis</i> cf. <i>crassicirrata</i> (Treadwell, 1925)	1	N		
Syllidae	<i>Syllis</i> cf. <i>profunda</i> Cognetti, 1955	2	Y	1	1
Syllidae	<i>Syllis garciai</i> (Campoy, 1982)	1	Y	1	3
Syllidae	<i>Syllis gracilis</i> Grube, 1840	4	Y	3	8
Syllidae	<i>Syllis prolifera</i> Krohn, 1852	1	Y	1	1
Syllidae	<i>Syllis similisunzima</i> San Martín, Lucas & Hutchings, 2023	2	Y	1	1
Syllidae	<i>Syllis truncata cryptica</i> Ben-Eliahu, 1977	3	Y	1	2

Family	Species	N° of individuals	Amplification success	N° of lineages (N)	N° of lineages (G)
Syllidae	<i>Syllis vittata</i> Grube, 1840	4	Y	2	3
Syllidae	<i>Trypanosyllis zebra</i> (Grube, 1860)	1	Y	1	15
Terebellidae	<i>Amphitrite</i> cf. <i>variabilis</i> (Risso, 1826)	3	Y	1	1
Terebellidae	<i>Amphitrite cirrata</i> O. F. Müller, 1776	1	Y	1	2
Terebellidae	<i>Amphitritides gracilis</i> (Grube, 1860)	1	Y	1	1
Terebellidae	<i>Eupolymnia</i> cf. <i>nesidensis</i> (Delle Chiaje, 1828)	3	Y	2	3
Terebellidae	<i>Eupolymnia nebulosa</i> (Montagu, 1819)	21	Y	2	4
Terebellidae	<i>Pista</i> sp.	2	Y	2	2
Terebellidae	<i>Terebella lapidaria</i> Linnaeus, 1767	3	Y	1	1
Terebellidae	<i>Thelepus parapari</i> Jirkov, 2018	3	Y	1	1
Terebellidae	<i>Thelepus triserialis</i> (Grube, 1855).	2	Y	1	1

During the development of the project MAPWORMS, among the features allowing annelid plasticity and adaptation to the environment, we identified the process of eversion/inversion of structures within the body of the worm as particularly interesting for biomimetic purposes; moreover, the ability of some worms to produce peristalsis in absence of segmentation appeared intriguing due to the simplified anatomies of these last in respect to the segmented relatives (Langeneck et al., 2023b). In this context, we identified as potential models both unsegmented annelids which are able to extend or evert parts of their body (species of Sipuncula and Echiura) and segmented annelids with an eversible pharynx (species of Amphinomida, Phyllodocida, Eunicida). The process of eversion of the introvert in Sipuncula and eversion of the pharynx in segmented annelids is rather similar, as the tip of the introvert/pharynx is a relatively small structure (the head of the Sipuncula in the case of the introvert, the pharyngeal bulb in the case of the pharynx) which maintains its orientation, while the remaining part of the structure changes orientation, with the internal surface becoming the external one after eversion. The main difference between the two systems is represented by the fact that the introvert of sipunculans experiences both an eversion and an elongation, and therefore the contracted organism is able to accommodate the entire introvert without needing additional internal space, while the pharynx of segmented annelids is not able to elongate, and when retracted is embedded into a specific chamber almost of the same length of the protruded pharynx. At the same time, pharynxes of segmented annelids are often armed with hard jaw pieces which might give an inspiration for inserting hard elements (e.g., surgical instruments) inside a soft robot without damaging it (Langeneck et al., 2023b). Among the species characterised from the molecular point of view, a soft, unsegmented body that is able to stretch is present in the echiuran *B. viridis*, and the sipunculans *A. muelleri* and *P. stephensoni* (Table 1), and the latter two species are also characterised by the presence of an eversible introvert. Eversible pharynxes with different extension and different combinations of hard parts occur in the species of the families Amphinomidae, Eunicidae, Glyceridae, Goniadidae, Lumbrineridae, Nephtyidae, Nereididae, Oeonidae, Phyllodocidae, Polynoidae, and Syllidae (Table 1); the comparison between different groups with different adaptations of the arrangement of muscular structures involved in the movements of the pharynx might help to understand the mechanics of the eversion process. Nonetheless, potential bioinspiring features occur in a wide array of other annelids; for instance, several sabellids including the species of the genus *Myxicola* are characterised by an extremely fast retraction speed enabled by the combination of continuous series of small hooks and fast-reacting muscles driven by giant axons (Prentiss et al., 2017); opheliid species of the genus *Ophelia* are characterised by a burrowing system led by two chambers separated by a single septum across which fluid can be moved allowing expansion or retraction of the body (Law et al., 2014); more generally, many marine annelids are able to adapt to the surrounding environment through dramatic changes in morphology (Trueman, 1966; Elder, 1973; Schembri & Jaccarini, 1977). Also considering the possibility of building chimaera soft robots inspired to the combination of morphological and biomechanic features occurring in different annelid groups, our characterisation of the

annelid diversity beyond the species able to evert part of their body ensured the creation of a catalogue of species/functions potentially useful to the overall aim of the project and its further evolution.

The percentual genetic identities retrieved after comparison with the available databases ranged between 70 and 100% for COI and between 75 and 100% for 16S. The distribution in classes of percentual identity was very similar for the two COI databases, while it was rather different for 16S sequences. In fact, for both markers and databases sequences with identity $\geq 97\%$ (typically considered within the intraspecific range – see Hebert et al., 2003) represent around 30% of the entries (Fig. 2); thus, sequences belonging to the same species are available for approximately 30% of the individuals assayed. In this case, the comparison with the sequences deposited in the BOLD database gave a higher percentage than GenBank (33% vs 27%), which is probably due to the higher number of COI sequences available on BOLD Systems (Fig. 2). However, part of the available sequences giving a $\geq 97\%$ match with the ones obtained in this study were identified only to the genus level, or to higher taxonomic levels (e.g., family or even as unidentified polychaete). Such uncertainties in the taxonomic assignment accounted for only 21% of the conspecific matches on GenBank, but for 34% of those on BOLD Systems, suggesting that, while BOLD is a more populated database and might seem better suited for the comparison of results from large-scale studies, it is also affected by a higher percentage of taxonomic uncertainty issues. By contrast, only 3% of the 16S sequences giving a $\geq 97\%$ match with the ones obtained in this study had uncertain taxonomic assignment. Sequences with identity between 97 and 90% accounted for a minor part of the COI dataset, while they represented approximately 1/3 of all 16S sequences obtained in the study; interestingly, due to the slightly different mutation rate, this identity percentage range is often considered ambiguous for COI (Kvist, 2016; Elgetany et al., 2020; Langeneck et al., 2022), while it is typically interspecific for 16S. Lastly, percentage identities below 90%, which are considered unambiguously interspecific for both markers, were more frequent for the COI dataset than for the 16S one (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 DISTRIBUTION OF GENETIC IDENTITIES (ID) BETWEEN THE SEQUENCES OBTAINED IN THE PRESENT WORK AND THOSE AVAILABLE IN PUBLIC ONLINE REPOSITORIES DEPENDING ON THE GENE (COI, 16S) AND THE DATABASE CONSULTED (GENBANK – GB, 16S, GREEN, COI, RED, AND BOLD, COI, YELLOW).

Molecular data allowed to correct some preliminary identifications of Deliverable 2.1 (Langeneck et al., 2023a). For instance, *Pareurythoe cf. borealis* (M. Sars, 1862) gave a 99.8% identity with the recently described *Cryptonome conclava*, a species hitherto known only for bathyal environments of the Levantine Sea, which is here reported for shallower environments and western localities; similarly, individuals identified as *Lumbrineris cf. geldiyi* Carrera-Parra, Çinar & Dağlı, 2011 gave a 100% identity with the Atlantic *Lumbrineris aniara*, and the provisional new species *Myxicola* sp. 2 corresponded to *M. polychroma*, described from the Atlantic Ocean after Deliverable 2.1 had been completed (Darbyshire, 2023). Lastly, the comparison with the available sequences highlighted some identification or labelling errors. For instance, *Aonides oxycephala* gave a 98% identity with a sequence assigned to the bivalve *Chamelea striatula* (da Costa, 1778) (presumably a labelling mistake); all 16S sequences of *Eurythoe complanata* had a 98.5% identity with a sequence assigned to *Diplocirrus glaucus*, but all COI sequences of the same individuals were identical to sequences of *E. complanata*, suggesting another case of mislabelling; a COI sequence of *Syllis gracilis* corresponded to sequences assigned to *Trypanosyllis zebra*, but its closeness with other members of the *S. gracilis* species complex suggests that previous identifications of this species as *T. zebra* were erroneous; COI sequences assigned to *Terebella lapidaria* corresponded to two morphospecies identified in this manuscript as *Terebella lapidaria* and *Amphitrite cf. variabilis*, suggesting a misidentification of a part of the sequences deposited in GenBank.

In Deliverable 2.1 we identified among the marine annelids reported for the Salento Peninsula 36 potential species complexes based on literature only. Multiple lineages were found in 18 out of the 143 species amplified (12.6%); due to the limited number of individuals assayed for each morphospecies, we usually identified 2 to 3 species co-occurring along the

coast of Salento; two remarkable exceptions are represented by *Perinereis cultrifera* (5 lineages) and *Amphiglena mediterranea* (7 lineages). The comparison with the data deposited in public repositories allowed to identify overall 46 cases (32% of all species assayed) where discrepancies between the sequences deposited under the same name supported the occurrence of a species complex. In particular, the presence of cryptic or pseudocryptic species was identified for the first time in *Amphiduros fuscescens*, *Amphitrite cirrata*, *Aonides oxycephala*, *Aricidea katzmanni*, *Asclerocheilus intermedius*, *Aspidosiphon muelleri*, *Bonellia viridis*, *Branchiomma bombyx*, *Dorvillea rubrovittata*, *Dorvillea similis*, *Eumida langenecki*, *Glycera alba*, *Gyptis propinqua*, *Lepidonotus clava*, *Marphysa chirigota*, *Myxicola* cf. *parasites*, *Naineris laevigata*, *Perinereis rullieri*, *Polyophthalmus pictus*, *Protomystides bidentata*, *Pseudopotamilla saxicava*, *Sclerocheilus minutus*, *Syllis truncata cryptica*, *Syllis vittata*. Cryptic lineages are widespread across all families, even if some families, as Syllidae, Nereididae and Sabellidae, are characterised by very high numbers of cryptic lineages within the same accepted morphospecies (e.g., *Perinereis cultrifera*: 13 lineages; *Trypanosyllis zebra*: 15 lineages; *Amphiglena mediterranea*: 18 lineages).

The opposite situation, namely, morphological differences that were not backed by molecular data, was found in a lesser percentage of the cases examined. In fact, cases of phenotypic plasticity and/or ontogenetic variation were identified for six molecular lineages (corresponding to 4% of the species for which molecular data were obtained). Phenotypic plasticity associated with local adaptation to different habitats was found in *Bispira viola*, *Phascolosoma stephensoni* and *Subadyte pellucida*. Individuals of *B. viola* from semi-enclosed, brackish and fully marine environments clearly differed in pigmentation and ultrastructure of the branchial crown, yet they were identical from the molecular point of view. A similar situation was found between individuals of *P. stephensoni* from the typical intertidal marine environment and much larger individuals occurring in sponges in port environments, tentatively identified as *P. granulatum*; despite the morphological and ecological differences, the two groups were genetically identical. The most striking case in this case is represented by *S. pellucida*, where individuals from port environments and from coralligenous environments showed constant differences in the structure of chaetae, supporting the hypothesis of two different species, but were identical from the genetic point of view. Phenotypic plasticity, i.e. the ability to undergo morphological changes in response to environmental pressures, is scantily studied in marine annelids, but it seems to be an important driver of adaptation for this group (Meyer et al., 2008; Syomin et al., 2017; Righi et al., 2019; Langeneck et al., 2020). Other cases of inconsistency between morphologically identified groups of organisms and genetic data are possibly related to developmental changes and to an incomplete understanding of growth processes in this group; two morphotypes identified as *Dasybranchus gajolae* and *Leiochrides* sp., showing different size and a different number of thoracic chaetigers (considered informative in Capitellidae) turned out to belong to the same species, and correspond to unidentified Capitellidae larvae sampled in a developing egg mass. Based on this finding, it is likely that thoracic chaetigers are subject

to a certain degree of variation during the development of this family. Also the individuals of *S. discifera*, a small, poorly known Sabellidae species, turned out to be identical to the widespread *S. spallanzanii*, and to just represent the juvenile form of this species. Lastly, the identity between two Goniadidae identified as *Goniada emerita* (with acicular notochaetae) and *Goniada hexadentes* (with capillary notochaetae) is deeply puzzling as it does not seem to have any obvious relationship with adaptation or development.

Finally, we obtained molecular data for the majority of the provisional species identified in Deliverable 2.1 (Langeneck et al., 2023a). In particular, molecular data were obtained for:

- *Axiokebuita* sp. 1 – first record of the genus in the Mediterranean Sea and from relatively shallow environments (all the congeneric species are either bathyal, or from cave environments). From the molecular point of view it is distinct from all congeneric species (identity > 90% for both COI and 16S). The species was also found in the Aegean Sea, and its description based on molecular data and morphology is currently under preparation.
- *Bispira* sp. 1 – aside from the two species already known for the area (*B. mariae* and *B. viola*), relatively deep bioconstructions host an undescribed species characterised by striking morphological differences, whose distinction is also supported by molecular data.
- *Dorvillea* sp. 1 – a lineage morphologically close to *Dorvillea similis*, albeit with longer antennae and palps and some slight differences in the jaw apparatus, turned out to be rather distant from the genetic point of view.
- *Eumida* sp. 1 – individuals sampled in the port of Brindisi correspond from the genetic and morphological point of view to a provisional new species known until now for a single specimen sampled in Orbetello Lagoon (Teixeira et al., 2022b). This species is characterised by a unique pigmentation pattern and by a remarkable tolerance to organic enrichment.
- *Eumida* aff. *ockelmanni* – some individuals sampled in the port of Brindisi (together with *Eumida* sp. 1) correspond from the genetic point of view to a potential new species found until now only off Taranto, in organically enriched environments (Teixeira et al., 2022b; Langeneck et al., 2023a). Initially identified as belonging to the *Eumida sanguinea* species complex, it turned out to be closer (but not identical) to the Atlantic *E. ockelmanni*.
- *Myxicola* sp. 2: small species, close to *Myxicola* cf. *parasites*, but genetically distinct and occurring in deep bioconstructions.
- *Myxicola* sp. 3: medium-sized species, with a striking live colour, occurring together with *M. giuliae* and *M. infundibulum* in shallow environments, clearly distinct from the genetic point of view from the *Myxicola infundibulum* species group (*sensu* Putignano et al., 2023) and with a closer relationship with *Myxicola* sp. 4.
- *Myxicola* sp. 4: small species, very similar in size, live colour and ecology to *Myxicola* cf. *parasites*, but very distant from the genetic point of view. Molecular data suggest

closeness with *Myxicola* sp. 3, but the two species have evident morphological differences and the genetic distance is higher than that retrieved between different species of the *Myxicola infundibulum* species group.

- *Neanthes* sp. 1: small species found in caves and sciaphilous environments off both Salento and Calabria. All specimens found are very small, possibly juveniles, and the examination of some characters (as the pharynx, which is diagnostic in this group) was impossible, but molecular data confirm its distinctness from all Mediterranean and Atlantic species for which data are available.
- *Ophryotrocha* sp. 1: rather large species, showing some similarities with *Ophryotrocha mammillata* Ravara, Marçal, Wiklund & Hilário, 2015, but morphologically and genetically distinct. The species was found in two localities off Salento and one in Greece and a detailed description, possibly taking advantage of microCT scans, is under preparation.
- *Perkinsiana* sp. 1: relatively deep species with uncertain generic attribution, sharing some characters typical of *Perkinsiana* and some typical of *Parasabella*. Molecular data are particularly scanty for Sabellidae and the sequence obtained does not show any particular similarity with any sequenced species.

Moreover, molecular data for 11 non-indigenous annelids recorded along the coast of Salento, corresponding in 8 cases to the first molecular data for the whole Mediterranean Sea, have been published (Langeneck et al., 2024) and manuscripts aimed at clarifying the diversity of *Dorvillea similis*, *Eupolymnia nebulosa*, *Eupolymnia nesidensis*, *Perinereis cultrifera*, *Perinereis rullieri* and *Polyopthalmus pictus* are currently under preparation.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The molecular characterisation of marine annelids sampled along the Salento Peninsula highlighted the wide occurrence of inconsistencies between the species identified based on morphological characters and the lineages retrieved through genetic characterisation, in agreement with previous works focusing on other geographic areas (Carr et al., 2011; Brasier et al., 2016; Oug et al., 2017). In fact, multiple lineages were identified in 46 out of the 143 morphospecies for which genetic characterisation was possible, corresponding to approximately one third. Assuming that this ratio is representative for all marine annelid species reported for the coast of Salento (around 650 – see Langeneck et al., 2023a), it can be inferred that more than 200 nominal taxa reported from the area will reveal themselves as species complexes and that our understanding of the actual diversity of marine annelids in the Mediterranean Sea is still far from complete. While in the majority of cases each morphospecies typically included two or three divergent lineages, some morphospecies (*A. mediterranea*, *P. cultrifera*, *T. zebra*) included more than ten lineages at the global scale, and in some cases (*A. mediterranea*, *P. cultrifera*) showed a remarkable diversity already in the study area, in agreement with previous studies (Nygren et al., 2018; Teixeira et al., 2022a; 2022b). Given the limited number of species hitherto sequenced and the lack of data from

the majority of Mediterranean locality, any estimate of the actual species diversity of marine annelids at the basin scale would be probably inaccurate; however, it is evident that the current estimate of ~1400 marine annelid species occurring in the Mediterranean Sea (Coll et al., 2010) is a gross underestimation, and a sizable part (possibly the majority) of the Mediterranean annelid biodiversity is still undescribed.

On the other hand, molecular data also shed light on the meaning of morphological characters that were traditionally considered as taxonomically informative. While the occurrence of pseudocryptic and cryptic species, i.e. the presence of a genetic variation that clearly overcomes morphological differences, is more frequent, in agreement with previous studies (e.g., Meyer et al., 2008; Syomin et al., 2017; Righi et al., 2019) we identified a minor part of cases where morphological differences are clearly more pronounced than genetic ones. Ecological adaptations and/or different growth rates can influence structural properties of the anatomy of the worm, suggesting the occurrence of different organisms even in presence of genetic homogeneity. The most significant case from the point of view of the project MAPWORMS is represented by *Phascolosoma stephensoni*; in this species bearing morphological, anatomical and behavioural features of particular interest for biomimetic purposes, individuals from port environments are characterised by much larger size and a thicker, more sculptured body wall, while those from open marine environments are much smaller and delicate. Body wall structure is not just an important character for sipunculan taxonomy (e.g., the presence of tubercles and papillae) but it also influences some structural properties that are important for modelling purpose (e.g., the elastic modulus). In this context, identifying diversity patterns and drivers in different sets of data is not just important from a biological perspective, but it can also give important information on morphological changes in model organisms and contribute to their use in bioinspiration.

5 REFERENCES

Ahrens J.B., Borda E., Barroso R., Paiva P.C., Campbell A.M., Wolf A., Nugues M.M., Rouse G.W., Schulze A. (2013) The curious case of *Hermodice carunculata* (Annelida: Amphinomidae): evidence for genetic homogeneity throughout the Atlantic Ocean and adjacent basins. *Molecular Ecology* 22: 2280-2291.

Aljanabi S.M., Martinez I. (1997) Universal and rapid salt-extraction of high quality genomic DNA for PCR-based techniques. *Nucleic Acids Research* 26: 4692-4693.

Arias A., Paxton H. (2015) The cryptogenic bait worm *Diopatra biscayensis* Fauchald et al., 2012 (Annelida: Onuphidae) – revisiting its history, biology and ecology. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 163: 22-36.

Bald J., Boria A., Muxika I., Franco J., Valencia V. (2005) Assessing reference conditions and physico-chemical status according to the European Water Framework Directive: A case-study from the Basque Country (Northern Spain). *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 50: 1508-1522.

- Bonifácio P., Martínez Arbizu P., Menot L. (2020) Alpha and beta diversity patterns of polychaete assemblages across the nodule province of the eastern Clarion-Clipperton Fracture Zone (equatorial Pacific). *Biogeosciences* 17: 865-886.
- Borja A., Franco J., Pérez V. (2000) A marine biotic index to establish the ecological quality of soft-bottom benthos within European estuarine and coastal environments. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 40: 1100-1114.
- Brasier M.J., Wiklund H., Neal L., Jeffreys R., Linse K., Ruhl H., Glover A.G. (2016) DNA barcoding uncovers cryptic diversity in 50% of deep-sea Antarctic polychaetes. *Royal Society Open Science* 3: 160432.
- Cabrol J., Winkler G., Tremblay R. (2015) Physiological condition and differential feeding behaviour in the cryptic species complex *Eurytemora affinis* in the St. Lawrence estuary. *Journal of Plankton Research* 37: 372-387.
- Caputi L., Andreakis N., Mastrototaro F., Cirino P., Vassillo M., Sordino P. (2007) Cryptic speciation in a model invertebrate chordate. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 104: 9364-9369.
- Carr C.M., Hardy S.M., Brown S.M., Macdonald T.A., Hebert P.D.N. (2011) A tri-oceanic perspective: DNA barcoding reveals geographic structure and cryptic diversity in Canadian polychaetes. *PLoS ONE* 6: e22232.
- Cheng Z., Li Q., Deng J., Liu Q., Huang X. (2023) The devil is in the details: Problems in DNA barcoding practices indicated by systematic evaluation of insect barcodes. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution* 11: 1149839.
- Cognetti Variabile A.M. (1967) Citotassonomia di alcune specie di Exogonine (Polychaeta, Syllidae). *Atti della Società dei Naturalisti e Matematici di Modena* 98: 106-108.
- Coll M., Piroddi C., Steenbeek J., Kaschner K., Ben Rais Lasram F., Aguzzi J., Ballesteros E., Bianchi C.N., Corbera J., Dailianis T., Danovaro R., Estrada M., Froglija C., Galil B.S., Gasol J.M., Gertwagen R., Gil J., Guilhaumon F., Kesner-Reyes K., Kitsos M.-S., Koukouras A., Lampadariou N., Laxamana E., Lopez-Fé de la Cuarda C.M., Lotze H.K., Martin D., Mouillot D., Oro D., Raicevich S., Rius-Barile J., Saiz-Salinas J.I., San Vicente C., Somot S., Templado J., Turon X., Vafidis D., Villanueva R., Voultsiadou E. (2010) The biodiversity of the Mediterranean Sea: estimates, patterns, and threats. *PLoS ONE* 5: e11842.
- Curini-Galletti M., Lardicci C., Regoli F. (1991) A contribution to the karyology of Syllidae (Polychaeta). *Ophelia* 5: 599-606.
- Darbyshire T. (2023) Designation of a neotype for *Myxicola infundibulum* (Montagu, 1808) (Annelida: Sabellidae) and a new species from the UK. *European Journal of Taxonomy* 900: 106-137.
- Derycke S., De Meester N., Rigaux A., Creer S., Bik H., Thomas W.K., Moens T. (2016) Coexisting cryptic species of the *Litoditis marina* complex (Nematoda) show differential resource use and have distinct microbiomes with high intraspecific variability. *Molecular Ecology* 25: 2093-2110.

Eilertsen M.H., Georgieva M.N., Kongsrud J.A., Linse K., Wiklund H., Glover A.G., Rapp H.T. (2018) Genetic connectivity from the Arctic to the Antarctic: *Scerolinum contortum* and *Nicomache lokii* (Annelida) are both widespread in reducing environments. *Scientific Reports* 8: 4810.

Ekman S. (1953) *Zoogeography of the Sea*. Sidgwick & Jackson, London, 417 pp.

Elder H.Y. (1973) Direct peristaltic progression and the functional significance of the dermal connective tissues during burrowing in the polychaete *Polyphysia crassa* (Oersted). *Journal of Experimental Biology* 58: 637-655.

Elgetany A.H., van Rensburg H., Hektoen M., Matthee C., Budaeva N., Simon C.A., Struck T.H. (2020) Species delineation in the speciation grey zone – the case of *Diopatra* (Annelida, Onuphidae). *Zoologica Scripta* 49: 516-534.

Fauchald K. (1984) Polychaete distribution patterns, or: can animals with Palaeozoic cousins show large scale geographical patterns? In: Hutchings P. (Ed.), *Proceedings of the First International Polychaete Conference*. The Linnean Society of New South Wales, Sidney, pp. 1-6.

Fauvel P. (1914) Annélides polychètes non-pélagiques provenant des campagnes del'Hirondelle et de la Princesse-Alice (1885-1910). *Résultats des Campagnes Scientifiques accomplies sur son yacht par Albert Ier Prince Souverain de Monaco* 46: 1-432.

Fauvel P. (1923) *Faune de France 5: Polychètes Errantes*. Paul Lechevalier, Paris, 488 pp.

Fauvel P. (1927) *Faune de France 16: Polychètes Sédentaires*. Paul Lechevalier, Paris, 494 pp.

Folmer O., Black M., Hoeh W., Lutz R., Vrijenhoek R. (1994) DNA primers for amplification of mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit I from diverse metazoan invertebrates. *Molecular Marine Biology and Biotechnology* 3: 294-299.

Furfaro G., Schreier C., Trainito E., Pontes M., Madrenas E., Girard P., Mariottini P. (2022) The sea slug *Doriopsilla areolate* Bergh, 1880 (Mollusca, Gastropoda) in the Mediterranean Sea: another case of cryptic diversity. *Diversity* 14: 297.

Geller J., Meyer C., Parker M., Hawk H. (2013) Redesign of PCR primers for mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit I for marine invertebrates and application in all-taxa biotic surveys. *Molecular Ecology Resources* 13: 851-861.

Golo R., Vergés A., Diaz-Tapia P., Cebrian E. (2023) Implications of taxonomic misidentification for future invasion predictions: Evidence from one of the most harmful invasive marine algae. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 191: 114970.

Grassle J., Grassle J.F. (1976) Sibling species in the marine pollution indicator *Capitella* (polychaeta). *Science* 192: 567-569.

Healey A.J.E., McKeown N.J., Taylor A.L., Provan J., Sauer W., Gouws G., Shaw P.W. (2018) Cryptic species and parallel genetic structuring in Lethrinid fish: Implications for conservation and management in the southwest Indian Ocean. *Ecology and Evolution* 8: 2182-2195.

- Hebert P.D.M., Cywinska A., Ball S.L., deWaard J.R. (2003) Biological identifications through DNA barcodes. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B* 270: 313-321.
- Jiu M., Hu J., Wang L.-J., Dong J.-F., Song Y.-Q., Sun H.-Z. (2017) Cryptic species identification and composition of *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) complex in Henan province, China. *Journal of Insect Science* 17: 78.
- Knowlton N. (1993) Sibling species in the sea. *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics* 24: 189-216.
- Knowlton N. (2000) Molecular genetic analyses of species boundaries in the sea. *Hydrobiologia* 420: 73-90.
- Kordbacheh A., Rahimian H., Fontaneto D. (2023) Mechanisms of reproductive isolation among cryptic species in monogonont rotifers. *Hydrobiologia* 850: 4705-4718.
- Korshunova T., Picton B., Furfaro G., Mariottini P., Pontes M., Prkić J., Fletcher K., Malmberg K., Lundin K., Martynov A. (2019) Multilevel fine-scale diversity challenges the 'cryptic species' concept. *Scientific Reports* 9: 6732.
- Kvist S. (2016) Does a global DNA barcoding gap exist in Annelida? *Mitochondrial DNA Part A* 27: 2241-2252.
- Langeneck J., Scarpa F., Maltagliati F., Sanna D., Barbieri M., Cossu P., Mikac B., Curini-Galletti M., Castelli A., Casu M. (2020) A complex species complex: the controversial role of ecology and biogeography in the evolutionary history of *Syllis gracilis* Grube, 1840 (Annelida, Syllidae). *Journal of Zoological Systematics and Evolutionary Research* 58: 66-78.
- Langeneck J., Fourreau C.J.L., Rousou M., Barbieri M., Maltagliati F., Musco L., Castelli A. (2022) Environmental features drive lineage diversification in the *Aricidea assimilis* species complex (Annelida, Paraonidae) in the Mediterranean Sea. *The European Zoological Journal* 89: 1246-1258.
- Langeneck J., Bilan M., Putignano M., Toso A., Musco L. (2023a) D2.1 Georeferenced Annelida distribution map along the Salento coast. Public report, project MAPWORMS, 88 pp.
- Langeneck J., Musco L., Quaglierini J., De Simone A., Keklikoglou K. (2023b) D2.2 First set of parameters for modelling. Public report, project MAPWORMS, 26 pp.
- Langeneck J., Putignano M., Dimichele D., Giangrande A., Bilan M., Toso A., Musco L. (2024) Non-indigenous polychaetes along the Salento Peninsula: new records and first molecular data. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 25: 184-203.
- Law C.J., Dorgan K.M., Rouse G.W. (2014) Relating divergence in polychaete musculature to different burrowing behaviors: a study using Opheliidae (Annelida). *Journal of Morphology* 275: 548-571.
- Lobo J., Teixeira M.A.L., Borges L.M.S., Ferreira M.S.G., Hollatz C., Gomes P.T., Sousa R., Ravara A., Costa M.H., Costa F.O. (2016) Starting a DNA barcode reference library for shallow water polychaetes from the southern European Atlantic coast. *Molecular Ecology Resources* 16: 298-313.

- Luttikhuizen P.C., Dekker R. (2010) Pseudo-cryptic species *Arenicola defodiens* and *Arenicola marina* (Polychaeta: Arenicolidae) in Wadden Sea, North Sea and Skagerrak: morphological and molecular variation. *Journal of Sea Research* 63: 17-23.
- Maltagliati F., Camilli L., Lardicci C., Castelli A. (2001) Evidence for morphological and genetic divergence in *Perinereis cultrifera* (Polychaeta: Nereididae) from two habitat types at Elba Island. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the U.K.* 81: 411-414.
- Maltagliati F., Peru A.P., Casu M., Rossi F., Lardicci C., Curini-Galletti M., Castelli A. (2000) Is *Syllis gracilis* (Polychaeta: Syllidae) a species complex? An allozyme perspective. *Marine Biology* 136: 871-879.
- Marques J.F., Santos M.J., Gibson D.I., Cabral H.N., Olson P.D. (2007) Cryptic species of *Didymobothrium rudolphii* (Cestoda: Spathebothriidea) from the sand sole, *Solea lascaris*, off the Portuguese coast, with an analysis of their molecules, morphology, ultrastructure and phylogeny. *Parasitology* 134: 1057-1072.
- Mayr E. (1942) *Systematics and the origin of species from the viewpoint of a zoologist*. Columbia University Press, 334 pp.
- McGovern T.M., Hellberg M.E. (2003) Cryptic species, cryptic endosymbionts, and geographical variation in chemical defences in the bryozoan *Bugula neritina*. *Molecular Ecology* 12: 1207-1215.
- Meyer A., Bleidorn C., Rouse G.W., Hausen H. (2008) Morphological and molecular data suggest a cosmopolitan distribution of the polychaete *Proscoloplos cygnochaetus* Day, 1954 (Annelida, Orbiniidae). *Marine Biology* 153: 879-889.
- Montesor M., Sgrosso S., Procaccini G., Kooistra W.H.C.F. (2003) Intraspecific diversity in *Scrippsiella trochoidea* (Dinophyceae): evidence for cryptic species. *Phycologia* 42: 56-70.
- Muangmai N., Preuss M., Zuccarello G.C. (2015) Comparative physiological studies on the growth of cryptic species of *Bostrychia intricata* (Rhodomelaceae, Rhodophyta) in various salinity and temperature conditions. *Phycological Research* 63: 300-306.
- Nygren A. (2014) Cryptic polychaete diversity: a review. *Zoologica Scripta* 43: 172-183.
- Nygren A., Parapar J., Pons J., Meißner K., Bakken T., Kongsrud J.A., Oug E., Gaeva D., Sikorski A., Johansen R.A., Hutchings P.A., Lavesque N., Capa M. (2018) A mega-cryptic species complex hidden among one of the most common annelids in the North East Atlantic. *PLoS ONE* 13: e0198356.
- Nygren A., Pleijel F. (2011) From one to ten in a single stroke – resolving the European *Eumida sanguinea* (Phyllodoceidae, Annelida) species complex. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 58: 132-141.
- Oliver P.M., Adams M., Doughty P. (2010) Molecular evidence for ten species and Oligo-Miocene vicariance within a nominal Australian gecko species (*Crenadactylus ocellatus*, Diplodactylidae). *BMC Evolutionary Biology* 10: 386.

- Oug E., Bakken T., Kongsrud J.A., Alvestad T. (2017) Polychaetous annelids in the deep Nordic Seas: Strong bathymetric gradients, low diversity and underdeveloped taxonomy. *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* 137: 102-112.
- Palumbi S., Martin A., Romano S., McMillan W.O., Stice L., Grabowski G. (1991) *The simple fool's guide to PCR, version 2.0*. Department of Zoology and Kewalo Marine Laboratory. University of Hawaii, Honolulu, the U.S.A.
- Prada C., Mcllroy S.E., Beltrán D.M., Valint D.J., Ford S.A., Hellberg M.E., Coffroth M.A. (2014) Cryptic diversity hides host and habitat specialization in a gorgonian-algal symbiosis. *Molecular Ecology* 23: 3330-3340.
- Prasanna H.C., Kanakala S., Archana K., Jyothisna P., Varma R.K., Malathi V.G. (2015) Cryptic species composition and genetic diversity within *Bemisia tabaci* complex in soybean in India revealed by *mtCOI* DNA sequence. *Journal of Integrative Agriculture* 14: 1786-1795.
- Prentiss N., Tyler M.S., Dean D. (2017) A morphological and histological investigation of the regeneration in *Myxicola infundibulum* (Montagu, 1808) (Sabellida, Annelida). *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the U.K.* 97: 1-11.
- Putignano M., Gravili C., Giangrande A. (2023) The peculiar case of *Myxicola infundibulum* (Polychaeta: Sabellidae): echo from a science 200 years old and description of four new taxa in the Mediterranean Sea. *The European Zoological Journal* 90: 506-546.
- Righi S., Maletti I., Maltagliati F., Castelli A., Barbieri M., Fai S., Prevedelli D., Simonini R. (2019) Morphometric and molecular characterisation of an expanding Ionian population of the fireworm *Hermodice carunculata* (Annelida). *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the U.K.* 99: 1569-1577.
- Roma-Marzio F., Najjar B., Alessandri J., Pistelli L., Peruzzi L. (2017) Taxonomy of the prickly juniper (*Juniperus oxycedrus* group): A phytochemical-morphometric combined approach at the contact zone of two cryptospecies. *Phytochemistry* 141: 48-60.
- Sanger F., Nicklen S., Coulson A.R. (1977) DNA sequencing with chain-terminating inhibitors. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 74: 5463-5467.
- Schembri P.J., Jaccarini V. (1977) Locomotory and other movements of the trunk of *Bonellia viridis* (Echiura, Bonelliidae). *Journal of Zoology* 182: 477-494.
- Schlick-Steiner B.C., Steiner F.M., Seifert B., Stauffer C., Christian E., Crozier R.H. (2010) Integrative taxonomy: a multisource approach to exploring biodiversity. *Annual Review of Entomology* 55: 421-438.
- Schulze A., Kawauchi G.Y. (2021) How many sipunculan species are hiding in our oceans? *Diversity* 13: 43.
- Serra V., Gammuto L., Nifla V., Castelli M., Lanzoni O., Sassera D., Bandi C., Sandeep B.V., Verni F., Modeo L., Petroni G. (2020) Morphology, ultrastructure, genomics, and phylogeny of *Euplotes vanleeuwenhoekii* sp. nov. and its ultrareduced endosymbiont "*Candidatus Pinguicoccus supinus*" sp. nov. *Scientific Reports* 10: 20311.

- Simboura N., Zenetos A. (2002) Benthic indicators to use in Ecological Quality classification of Mediterranean soft bottom marine ecosystems, including a new Biotic Index. *Mediterranean Marine Science* 3: 77-111.
- Sonneborn T.M. (1939) *Paramecium aurelia*: mating types and groups; lethal interactions; determination and inheritance. *American Naturalist* 73: 390-413.
- Sun Y., Kupriyanova E.K., Qiu J.-W. (2012) COI barcoding of *Hydroides*: A road from impossible to difficult. *Invertebrate Systematics* 26: 539-547.
- Syomin V., Sikorski A.V., Bastrop R., Köhler N. (2017) The invasion of the genus *Marenzelleria* (Polychaeta, Spionidae) into the Don River mouth and the Taganrog Bay: morphological and genetic study. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the U.K.* 97: 975-984.
- Tan D.S.H., Ang Y., Lim G.S., Bin Ismail M.R., Meier R. (2010) From 'cryptic species' to integrative taxonomy: an iterative process involving DNA sequences, morphology and behaviour leads to the resurrection of *Sepsis pyrrhosoma* (Sepsidae: Diptera). *Zoologica Scripta* 39: 51-61.
- Teixeira M.A.L., Langeneck J., Vieira P.E., Hernández J.C., Sampieri B.R., Kasapidis P., Mucciolo S., Bakken T., Ravara A., Nygren A., Costa F.O. (2022a) Reappraisal of the hyperdiverse *Platynereis dumerilii* (Annelida: Nereididae) species complex in the Northern Atlantic, with the description of two new species. *Invertebrate Systematics* 36: 1017-1061.
- Teixeira M.A.L., Vieira P.E., Ravara A., Costa F.O., Nygren A. (2022b) From 13 to 22 in a second stroke: revisiting the European *Eumida sanguinea* (Phyllodocidae: Annelida) species complex. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society* 196: 169-197.
- Töpfer-Hofmann G., Cordes D., von Helversen O. (2000) Cryptic species and behavioural isolation in the *Pardosa lugubris* group (Araneae: Lycosidae), with description of two new species. *Bulletin of the British Arachnological Society* 11: 257-274.
- Trueman E.R. (1966) The mechanism of burrowing in the polychaete worm *Arenicola marina* (L.). *Biological Bulletin of the Marine Biology Laboratory, Woods Hole* 131: 369-377.
- Viard F., Roby C., Turon X., Bouchemousse S., Bishop J. (2019) Cryptic diversity and database errors challenge non-indigenous species surveys: an illustration with *Botrylloides* spp. In the English Channel and Mediterranean Sea. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 6: 615.
- Weigand H., Beermann A.J., Ciampor F., Costa F.O., Casabai Z., Duarte S., Geiger M.F., Grabowski M., Rimet F., Rulik B., Strand M., Szucsich N., Weigand A.M., Willassen E., Wyler S., Bouchez A., Borja A., Ciamporova-Zatovicova Z., Ferreira S., Dijkstra K.-D.B., Eisendle U., Freythof J., Gadawski P., Graf A., Haegerbaeumer A., van der Hoorn B.B., Japoshvili B., Keresztes L., Keskin E., Leese F., Macher J.N., Mamos T., Paz G., Pesic V., Maric Pfannkuchen D., Pfannkuchen M.A., Price B.W., Rinkevich B., Teixeira M.A.L., Varbiro G., Ekrem T. (2019) DNA barcode reference libraries for the monitoring of aquatic biota in Europe: Gap-analysis and recommendations for future work. *Science of the Total Environment* 678: 499-524.
- Whitesides G.M. (2015) Bioinspiration: something for everyone. *Interface Focus* 5: 20150031.

Yeates D.K., Seago A., Nelson L., Cameron S.L., Joseph L., Trueman J.W.H. (2011) Integrative taxonomy, or iterative taxonomy? *Systematic Entomology* 36: 209-217.

Zhang X.M., Wang S., Li S., Luo C., Li Y.X., Zhang F. (2015) Comparison of the antennal sensilla ultrastructure of two cryptic species in *Bemisia tabaci*. *PLoS ONE* 10: e0121820.